

Controlled synthesis of nanocrystalline glass-like carbon thin films with tuneable electrical and optical properties

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Abstract

Graphene is an emerging electronic material but expensive and difficult to produce in pure, large-area thin films. Organic electronic applications such as flexible devices and energy applications would benefit from low-cost alternatives to graphene. The controlled synthesis of nanometer-thin carbon films by atmospheric pressure chemical vapor deposition on copper foils is presented. These nanostructured carbon thin films (5–237 nm of thickness) are composed of curved graphene fullerene-like fragments of *ca.* 3 nm average size, which replicate the structure of widely used glass-like carbons. The optical and electrical properties of these nanostructured carbon thin films are defined by their thickness of these films; high transparency (86%) and moderate high electrical conductivity ($7.8 \text{ k}\Omega/\square$) are achieved for the thinnest samples (5 nm). Although these values are in the range of other thin films prepared with graphene, these films are fundamentally different since they are composed entirely of graphene flakes joined by a carbon matrix, which presents a high density of defects; thus they are also interesting candidates for flexible and transparent electronics, especially when biocompatibility, friction, high temperature, UV radiation, and corrosion resistance are also needed.

1. Introduction

Carbon is a very versatile element, and is able to form a great variety of crystalline structures such as graphene, nanotubes, nanofibers and fullerenes [1]–[4], and disordered structures such as diamond-like carbon, glass-like carbon, carbon black, and amorphous carbon [5]–[7]. Since the in-depth characterization of graphene properties in 2004 [8], there has been renewed interest in carbon nanomaterials as thin films for a wide variety of applications, such as energy production/storage, biocompatible scaffolds, and electronics, among others [9]–[12]. Despite the potential of graphene for so many applications, the large-scale production of atomically thin and monocrystalline graphene film has not yet been achieved [13]–[17]. Alongside the ongoing work on graphene, the synthesis and use of other carbon nanomaterials with lower degrees of crystallinity might relax the requirements of production and manipulation processes such as highly controlled atmospheres, substrate preconditioning, sample transfer, etc. Such materials should still have great potential and applicability for flexible electronics because of their high transparency and electrical conductivity, among other interesting properties, and may complement the existing current portfolio of carbon nanomaterials.

Glass-like forms of carbon are a good example of disordered sp^2 -hybridized carbon materials. The structure of these glass-like carbon materials consists of nearly 100% sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms, which forms randomly oriented fullerene-like fragments of different sizes, depending on the intensity of the heat treatment used for their production [18]–[23]. The name of this form of carbon comes from its glass-like appearance, but is now also used for materials with similar structures [24]–[26]. Glass-like forms of carbon combine interesting properties such as high temperature stability, extreme resistance to chemical corrosion, high hardness, low density, and high impermeability to both gases and liquids [20], [23], [27] and are already used as electrode materials and crucibles. Interestingly, glass-like forms of carbon can also be produced in thin films that are as transparent as graphene films of similar thickness, by pyrolyzing a photoresist resin [28]. In this way, interesting functional materials such as flexible neuroelectronic implants for dopamine sensing were recently obtained [29]. Carbon materials with a similar disordered structure of single-layered curved and defective graphene sheets, can also have an exceptional specific surface area due to their high density of edge defects, which are of great interest for energy-storage applications

[12], [30]. This embedded nanocrystallites within an amorphous carbon matrix can induce strong paramagnetism [31]–[34], which is ascribed to the presence of a spin magnetic moment at the graphene layer edges. In summary, the presence of nanoscale crystals and defects in carbon materials may induce interesting properties through the development of nanoporosity or crystal defects, which have advantages for advanced applications over the more crystalline forms of carbon such as graphene or nanotubes.

Here, we study the controlled synthesis of nanocrystalline glass-like carbon thin films (area *ca.* 10cm²) directly on copper foils by atmospheric chemical vapor deposition. We follow a similar process to that used in production of graphene films [35], but using a wide range of gas concentrations to enable easy film-thickness control. We obtain transparent and conductive glass-like carbon thin films formed by randomly oriented and curved graphitic nanocrystallites within an amorphous carbon matrix. Finally, we study the optical and electrical parameters of our thin glass-like carbon films, showing the ability to tune both optical and electrical parameters by controlling the film thickness.

2. Experimental

Materials. A commercial copper foil was used as catalyst for the chemical vapor deposition of the carbon films (100- μ m-thick copper foil, 99.8% purity, Sigma Aldrich). The copper foil was cut into rectangles of 22 \times 50 mm². The copper samples were dipped in pure ethanol and cleaned by ultrasonication for 10 min. No additional pretreatment of the copper foils was carried out.

Chemical vapor deposition of carbon films. We used a custom-made chemical vapor deposition reactor [37], which consisted of a longitudinal mobile tubular furnace, to perform the fast heat approach [38]. All the gas lines (Ar, H₂, and C₂H₄) connected to the 22-mm diameter quartz tube were flushed for 10 min, followed by an additional 10 min of Ar to displace trapped air and other gases from the system. The furnace was then ramped to the synthesis temperature (850°C) with 1000/20 sccm of Ar/H₂ flowing, while keeping the sample outside the heating zone. Once the temperature stabilized, the furnace was rapidly moved (*ca.* 3 s) to locate the center of the heating zone of the furnace around the copper foil. Prior to the last synthesis step, 10 min of annealing with 1000/20 sccm of Ar/H₂ flow was used. Several synthesis conditions were tested to study

the effect of the total gas flow ($Q = \text{Ar} + \text{H}_2 + \text{C}_2\text{H}_4$) and the ethylene concentration $[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4] = \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 / (\text{Ar} + \text{H}_2 + \text{C}_2\text{H}_4)$. The total flow varied from 140 to 540 sccm and the ethylene concentration from 0.04 to 0.5. The synthesis time was fixed at 5 min. After the synthesis, the furnace was moved away from the sample to allow rapid cool-down under Ar flow. Details of the process can be found in the Supplementary Information (Figure S1) and elsewhere [37].

Carbon film thickness. As-synthesized samples were dipped in $\text{FeCl}_3 - \text{HCl}$ copper etching solution (Sigma Aldrich, 667528) to dissolve the copper foil. Once the glass-like carbon film was detached in the form of flakes, they were cleaned by replacing the etchant with deionized water and washing several times. The carbon flakes were transferred into a thermal oxide wafer (300 nm SiO_2 on Si). Atomic force microscopy characterization (non-contact mode, Park XE150) was carried out.

Carbon film microstructure. Carbon flakes from three thin carbon films (thickness <15 nm) were transferred onto a copper grid for analysis under a transmission electron microscope (JEOL JEM 3000F). Raman spectra of all the samples were collected from on top of silicon wafers (Jasco, NRS-5100). At least three measurements per synthesis condition were taken, using a Nd:YAG green laser (532 nm, aperture: 4000 μm , grating: 1800 l/mm, slit: 200×1000 μm , resolution: 7.42 cm^{-1}), with two accumulations of 20 s exposure over a range of 1000–3250 cm^{-1} . The effective laser power was about 5.3 mW. We compared the Raman spectra of our carbon films with those of a glass-like carbon rod (Gomensoro, N°61248040) and graphene sheet on a silicon wafer (Graphenea). We also analyzed the spectra of all the carbon films synthesized within this work.

We carried out an additional Raman experiment to ascertain if the layer that is in contact with the copper foil, (“bottom carbon”), has a different Raman spectra than that of the carbon on the top (“top carbon”). (Supplementary Information, Figure S4). The analysis of the Raman spectra of the carbon films was carried out by fitting the corresponding band of highly disordered carbons as proposed in several articles [36], [39], [40].

Electrical Characterization. The thinner carbon films (<20 nm) were spin-coated with poly(methylmethacrylate) (PMMA; 495PMMA A Resists, Microchem). Copper was

etched away (using Sigma Aldrich 667528), and finally the carbon thin film/PMMA was electrically characterized. In a standard probe station the needles pierced the thinner samples so, to avoid sample destruction, the sheet resistance of the samples was measured by using contactless conductivity equipment LEI88 (Leighton Electronics Inc.). Each measurement was performed at least 20 times, hence the uncertainty interval for each sample.

Optical Characterization. Transmission measurements were performed on the carbon thin film (<20 nm thick)/PMMA samples by using spectroscopic reflectometry–transmission equipment on a Canon microscope (Sentech FTP). Measurements were obtained by using a $\times 10$ microscope objective that provided a spot with a diameter of around 20 μm .

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Thickness control through CVD parameters

We were able to define the thickness of our produced films, and thus their optical and electrical properties, by careful control of the gas flow ratios used in CVD. Carbon films from 5–237 nm thick were synthesized on top of the copper foil (Figure 1). As expected, the ethylene concentration had a positive effect on the carbon film thickness, which can be clearly observed at a total flow of 140 sccm. However, this dependence of film thickness on total flow was not so evident at higher total flows. Higher total flows at a given ethylene concentration also resulted in thinner carbon films. This effect was clear only for higher ethylene concentrations [41]. Thin films of 5–10 nm were obtained by using highly diluted ethylene and high total flows, meanwhile thick films of about 80 nm were obtained by using highly concentrated ethylene and low total flows.

The relationship between experimental conditions and outcome is a balance of factors. From the results obtained, the lower the time the hydrocarbon molecules of the decomposed ethylene are in contact with the substrate and the fewer molecules, the thinner the carbon film synthesized on the substrate. As expected, these thin films are obtained at the higher total flows and the lower ethylene concentrations. We have developed a simple model that captures the effects of both the ethylene concentration and the total flow on the film thickness. Our model results are in agreement with our experimental data (Figure 1). We found that this carbon deposition process is not exclusive to copper substrates; for example, we also deposited a carbon layer on top of quartz slides or even on the walls of the quartz tube for high ethylene concentration and low total flows. However, as the copper substrate has a catalytic effect on the carbon deposited, the microstructure of the carbon layer deposited on top of copper catalysts may show better graphitization than that of carbon films on quartz. Details of the experimental conditions and this model can be seen in Table 1 and in the Supplementary Information.

3.2 Microstructure of carbon films

3.2.1 Transmission electron microscopy. We have analyzed the microstructure of the carbon thin films produced by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The carbon films were composed of randomly oriented and curved crystallites within an amorphous carbon matrix. The curved graphene layer fragments resemble the fullerene-like fragments that form glass-like carbons [19]–[23]. Exemplary TEM images show the curved graphene layer fragments with a maximum size of about 3 nm (Figure 2a), as well as semicontinuous graphitic planes similar to those seen in few-layer graphene (Figure 2b). Glass-like forms of carbon can be obtained at different temperatures [20], [22], which results in different crystal lengths. As proposed in reference [23], type-I glass-like carbons are produced below 2000°C, which consist of randomly distributed curved graphene-layer fragments with open pores, while type-II glass-like carbons are fabricated at higher temperatures and contain longer range and self-assembled fullerene-like spheroids with closed pores. Here, we obtained type-I glass-like carbon, since our film has randomly distributed and open curved graphene-layer fragments within an amorphous matrix. TEM images of carbon films with varying thicknesses can be found in the Supplementary Information, Figure S6.

3.2.2. Raman spectroscopy. In order to learn about the crystal structure of our carbon thin films, we performed Raman spectroscopy. To compare the Raman spectra of our carbon films with other similar carbon forms with different degrees of order, the Raman spectra of a 5-nm-thick carbon film synthesized in our laboratory, that of a glass-like carbon rod, and that of a graphene sheet are represented in Figure 3a. In the Raman spectra of carbons, the G peak at about 1580 cm^{-1} (assigned to the high frequency E_{2g} Raman-allowed optical phonon) corresponds to the bond stretching of sp^2 carbon pairs in both rings and chains. The disorder in the microstructure of graphite is mostly evidenced by the appearance of the D peak at around 1350 cm^{-1} (assigned to the an A_{1g} phonon at **K**), which corresponds to the breathing modes of sp^2 carbon rings, but also by the G band broadening (D' peak *ca.* 1620 cm^{-1}) and the presence of a D'' band (*ca.* 1100 cm^{-1}). These first-order phonons may combine, which would explain second-order peaks at D+D'' *ca.* 2450 cm^{-1} and D+D' *ca.* 2950 cm^{-1} . Finally, 2D (*ca.* 2700 cm^{-1}) and 2D' (*ca.* 3250 cm^{-1}) peaks are the D and D' overtones respectively, and although these are not only activated when defect are present, they do broaden in disordered graphites [36], [42]–[45]. All

these disorder-related effects in the Raman scattering of graphites are easily visible in the commercial glass-like carbon rod and our 5-nm-thick carbon film, although not in the more crystalline graphene (Figure 3a). In fact, additional peaks related to disordered carbon at about 1240 and 1480 cm^{-1} were also present in the Raman spectra of the 5-nm-thick carbon films (Figure 3b) [46], [47]. All this shows that our glass-like carbon samples are highly disordered, in agreement with TEM observations. We measured the Raman spectra of all the carbon films synthesized here to compare their degree of disorder.

We analyzed the full width half maximum of D and G peaks (FWHM_D , FWHM_G) and the ratio between both intensities, I_D/I_G after fitting (see experimental conditions). As can be clearly observed in the Raman spectra in Figure 4a, as the films become thinner the D peak narrows and increases in height compared to the G peak. The I_D/I_G ratio is widely used as a measure of the degree of disorder of the in-plane crystal size (L_a) of carbon materials, since the D peak arises from defects that decrease the crystal size. When in-plane crystal size is above *ca.* 3 nm, I_D/I_G and L_a are inversely related by the Tuinstra and Koenig relation, $L_a \propto (I_D/I_G)^{-1}$, which is the general behavior observed for graphene-related materials. However, when the in-plane crystal size is below *ca.* 3 nm many of the sp^2 -hybridized carbon rings open up and the vibration modes that produce the D peak can not take place. In this scenario, the increment in the D peak is related to larger crystal size, following the relation $L_a^2 \propto (I_D/I_G)$ [36]. In our samples, I_D/I_G clearly increases for thinner films (Figure 4a,b) and since the ordered regions identified by TEM (Figure 2a,b) are smaller than 3 nm, below the Tuinstra and Koenig limit, our films follow the direct relation $L_a^2 \propto (I_D/I_G)$, which means that thinner films have a higher degree of order. This result can also be extracted by the analysis of the FWHM_D (Figure 4c), which is known to be narrow in ordered graphites and broader in disordered forms of carbon. In-plane crystal size, L_a , can be deduced by analysis of the FWHM_G (Figure 4d), as both correlate directly [5]. From these works we believe to have an average crystal size of around 3 nm for the more crystalline sample; this result coincides with the TEM observation ($\text{FWHM}_G \approx 60 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), and below 1 nm for the more disordered ($\text{FWHM}_G \approx 75 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

3.2.3 Carbon film anisotropy through the thickness. By modifying the total gas flow and the ethylene concentration, we controlled the sample thickness. As the temperature, annealing, and synthesis time are constant for all the samples, the difference in their

Raman spectra might be due to the catalytic effect of the copper which only affects the crystallinity of the carbon film closer to the foil [48].

We identified by the analysis of I_D/I_G ratio and the $FWHM_{D,G}$ that the “bottom carbon film”, which was in contact with the copper foil during CVD, has a higher degree of order than the carbon deposited as the CVD progresses (“top carbon film”) (Figure 4f). We highlight here that the Raman laser used (532 nm) has a probing depth of about 100 nm in amorphous carbon [49]–[51], so the more crystalline “bottom carbon film” is not fully reached by the Raman laser in thick films (Figure 4g). This anisotropy through the thickness of the film [52], explains why thick carbon films showed less-ordered Raman spectra than the thin ones, as all the samples were analyzed on the top surface of the film (Figure 4e). This amorphous film structure can be also seen by TEM in Figure 2b. These results highlight the importance of examining the film in its entirety rather than relying on Raman analysis, in films above a certain thickness. Although we found that carbon films can be deposited on several substrates, such as quartz slides or copper films (Supplementary Information Figure S2), copper combines a very low carbon solubility, catalytic activity and high flexibility that makes it a unique catalyst for scalable roll-to-roll CVD systems [13]. Since we are looking for a process to produce films with high levels of crystallinity and which is easy to scale-up, thermal CVD using copper foils is a convenient approach, although other processes like plasma-enhanced CVD can also be used to lower the synthesis temperature.

Most CVD-graphene recipes from the literature [13] use highly diluted methane as the hydrocarbon source, however, we used highly concentrated ethylene. Due to the high ethylene concentration the carbon deposition rate on the surface of copper is faster than the graphene crystal nucleation and growth rate during the CVD process [48], [53], thus, a through-thickness anisotropic carbon film is produced on top of the copper. This film is composed of a semicontinuous few-layer graphene film, due to the catalytic action of the copper substrate, followed by a layer of curved graphene nanocrystals on top. We are not aware of a similar material and we believe that this through-thickness anisotropy may be useful for several applications that we are also studying at present.

3.3 Optical and electrical studies of carbon films

High optical transmittance and good electrical conductivity are important in applications such as touch screens, transparent electrodes, liquid crystal displays, etc. We analyzed the transmittance (Supplementary Information, Figure S7) and the electrical conductivity of the thinnest carbon films (<20 nm) which were transparent, to some degree, to the naked eye. The sheet electrical resistance (R_s) and transmittance (T) at 550 nm decrease with the thickness of the film (Figure 5a,b). As expected, thicker films are more conductive and less transparent. We calculated the electrical conductivities (σ_{DC}) of the carbon films to be $\sigma_{DC}=8.7\times 10^3-2.5\times 10^4$ S/m. Comparing with the literature, these values are lower than bulk highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (2.50×10^6 S/m), similar to bulk glass-like carbon and pyrolyzed photoresist thin films, and well above those of amorphous carbon (10^2 S/m) [6], [54]. The large error obtained in some measurements is attributed to damage during the transfer of the carbon film to PMMA [13]. We reviewed some results of disordered carbon thin films, synthesized from 400°C to 1100°C, on different substrates, such as silicon wafers; these showed values up to $R_s=100$ k Ω/\square T=93% at 950°C and 20 Torr [55], or up to 6 k Ω/\square and 80% at 1100°C on sapphire [54], [56]. Other work on deposition of carbon films on Cu foils at 1000°C resulted in 0.717 k Ω/\square at 41.4%, 1.6 k Ω/\square at 80%, or 610 k Ω/\square at 96% [57]–[59], so our films show better coupled properties, $R_s=7.836$ k Ω/\square and T=85.66%, than other materials synthesized on similar substrates and using lower synthesis temperatures (Supplementary Information, Figure S7).

One of the potential applications of carbon thin films is as transparent and flexible electrodes for electronic displays/touch panels, organic light-emitting diodes, solar cells, and antistatic coatings [60]. A good measure of the suitability of a material for these applications is given by a single parameter, the σ_{DC}/σ_{OP} ratio, which incorporates both electrical (σ_{DC}) and optical (σ_{OP}) conductivities,

$$\frac{\sigma_{DC}}{\sigma_{OP}} = \frac{\frac{Z_0}{2R_s}}{T^{-\frac{1}{2}}-1} \quad (2)$$

where Z_0 is the characteristic impedance of vacuum (*ca.* 377 Ω), T the film thickness, and R_s its sheet resistance. The best values of σ_{DC}/σ_{OP} ratio for our carbon films are about 0.3,

similar to that of thin films prepared with graphene and graphene oxide flakes [61]. However, as our film is composed entirely of graphene crystals joined by carbon, we believe that, by optimizing the process, these values can be improved.

4. Concluding remarks and future work

We have studied the synthesis of carbon thin films on top of copper foils, by the chemical vapor deposition of Ar, H₂, and C₂H₄. Carbon film thicknesses from 5–237 nm were obtained by tuning the gas flow rates from 40–540 sccm and ethylene concentration from 0.04–0.5. The resulting carbon film thicknesses were proportional to the ethylene concentration and inversely proportional to the gas flow. Transmission electron microscopy and Raman spectroscopy showed that the carbon films were formed by randomly oriented curved graphene nanocrystallites which showed order in ranges up to 3 nm, which resembles the fullerene-like fragments that form glass-like carbons.

Raman results demonstrated that, as the CVD progresses and the carbon film thickness increases, the carbon is deposited with lower degree of order, so higher degree of order was achieved in contact with the copper foil. Consequently, thinner films were more crystalline than the thicker films, which were formed of a thin and crystalline region underneath a thick and disordered region. We obtained optical transmittance up to 86%, and electrical conductivities similar to those of bulk glass-like forms of carbon (10^4 S/m) and well above that of amorphous carbon. As opposed to other polymer thin films that are reinforced with graphene and graphene oxide flakes, the films synthesized here are composed entirely of graphene crystals joined by carbon; thus these films are also of great interest for flexible and transparent electronics, when biocompatibility, high temperature, UV radiation and corrosion resistance are required.

Competing financial interests

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

5. Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Program, NFRP project, PICIG12-GA-2012-33924. R.G.V. gratefully acknowledges the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation for financial funding through the Ramon y Cajal Fellowship. The authors would like to thank J.C. Rubalcaba for early discussions and work on the chemical vapor deposition reactor, M. Terrones and A. L. Elías (Penn State), early work on the chemical vapor deposition synthesis and the transfer process, A. Gomez (CNME, UCM) for TEM imaging assistance, and M. Monclus (IMDEA Materials Institute) for AFM assistance.

Tables

Table 1. Conditions of the chemical vapor deposition process in the synthesis of the carbon film with C₂H₄ as precursor gas. The temperature was kept for 5 min at 850°C. No more CVD conditions were carried out for total gas flow (Q) of 40 sccm due to technical limitations of our flow controllers.

Q=40 sccm		Q=140 sccm		Q=340 sccm		Q=540 sccm	
Ar-H ₂ -C ₂ H ₄	[C ₂ H ₄]	Ar-H ₂ -C ₂ H ₄	[C ₂ H ₄]	Ar-H ₂ -C ₂ H ₄	[C ₂ H ₄]	Ar-H ₂ -C ₂ H ₄	[C ₂ H ₄]
–	–	120-10-10	0.07	300-20-20	0.06	500-20-20	0.04
–	–	100-20-20	0.14	190-75-75	0.22	420-60-60	0.11
–	–	80-30-30	0.21	140-100-100	0.29	300-120-120	0.22
0-20-20	0.5	0-70-70	0.5	0-170-170	0.5	0-270-270	0.50

Figures

Figure 1. Thickness of carbon films as a function of CVD parameters (total flow from 40–540 sccm and ethylene concentration from 0.04–0.5). The ethylene concentration had a clear proportional effect on the carbon film thickness at total flows of 140 sccm, but there was no evident linearity at 340 and 540 sccm. The higher the total flow, the thinner the carbon films produced; this effect is especially significant at higher ethylene concentrations. We have proposed a simple model for the film thickness as a function of the ethylene concentration and the total flow that is in agreement with our experimental data. (See Supplementary Information).

Figure 2. Transmission electron microscopy image of a 5-nm-thick carbon film. The carbon films are composed of randomly oriented and curved crystallites with sizes of up to 3 nm within an amorphous carbon matrix, which resembles the microstructure of glass-like carbons. b) A wrinkle on the same sample, in which some semicontinuous graphitic planes can be seen, similar to those in few-layered graphene (up to 5–10 layers).

Figure 3. Raman spectroscopy studies of a) our 5-nm-thick carbon thin films, commercial graphene, and a glass-like carbon rod. The disorder in the microstructure of glass-like carbon rod and our carbon film is evidenced by the appearance of the D peak at *ca.* 1350 cm^{-1} , the G band broadening (D' peak *ca.* 1620 cm^{-1}), and the D'' band (*ca.* 1200 cm^{-1}). The peaks at *ca.* 2450 cm^{-1} and *ca.* 2950 cm^{-1} are the combination of D, D', and D'' bands. Peaks at *ca.* 2700 cm^{-1} and 3250 cm^{-1} are the D and D' overtones respectively. b) An additional peak related to disordered carbon at about 1480 cm^{-1} was

also present in the Raman spectra of the 5-nm-thick carbon films. (*Raman contribution of Si wafer support on graphene and thin carbon film).

Figure 4. Raman spectra of all carbon films synthesized on the copper foil. a) As the films get thinner, the D peak narrows and increases compared to the G peak. The Raman contribution of the Si wafer substrate is detected for films up to 20 nm-thick*. b) Given the size of the crystals detected by TEM ($L_a < 3$ nm), I_D/I_G follows the direct relation $L_a^2 \propto (I_D/I_G)$ [36], which means that thinner films are more crystalline. c) The $FWHM_D$ confirms that thinner films are more crystalline than the thick ones. d) In-plane crystal size L_a can be deduced by analysis of the $FWHM_G$ [5]; we have an average crystal size of *ca.* 3 nm for the more crystalline sample. This value coincides with results from the TEM observation ($FWHM_G \approx 60$). The average crystal size is below 1 nm for the more disordered ($FWHM_G \approx 75$) areas. e) A proposed growth mechanism of the carbon films, which are composed of a few-layer graphene region underneath a region formed by fullerene-like fragments. f) The “bottom carbon” which was in contact with the copper foil during CVD, has a higher degree of order than the “top carbon”, as

detected in a 14-nm-thick carbon film and g) a 237-nm-thick carbon film. Despite the Raman laser of 532 nm has a probe depth of about 100 nm, the contribution of the top region of the carbon film to the Raman spectra is higher than that of the bottom region.

Figure 5. Electrical and optical performance of carbon films. The sheet resistance (R_s) and transmittance at 550 nm (T) decreases with the thickness of the films, showing limiting values of $R_s=7.836\pm 1.500$ k Ω/\square coupled with $T=85.66\%$ (for a 5-nm-thick carbon film), and $R_s=4.298\pm 0.140$ k Ω/\square at $T=58.65\%$ (for 18-nm-thick carbon film).

6. Supplementary Information

Film thickness Model. We found a simple relation for the carbon film thickness that can be adjusted to our experimental results. The film thickness is proportional to the ethylene concentration and inversely proportional to the average speed of the gas, as follows:

$$\text{Carbon Film Thickness} = C \cdot t \cdot \frac{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4]}{\langle V \rangle} = C \cdot t \cdot \frac{[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4]}{Q/A}$$

where C is a proportionality constant, t the synthesis time (5 min), $\langle V \rangle$, the average speed of the gas at the entrance of the CVD (at standard conditions). Q, the total flow, and A, the area of the quartz tube (2.2 cm of inner diameter). We adjusted this equation ($C=1.020 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2/\text{min}^2$), as can be seen in Figure 1.

Table S1. Conditions of the chemical vapor deposition process in the synthesis of the carbon film with C_2H_4 as precursor gas. The temperature was kept for 5 min at 850°C . Thickness, sheet resistance, and transmittance at 550 nm are also provided.

Q (sccm)	CVD Gas Ar-H ₂ -C ₂ H ₄ (sccm)	Average speed $\langle V \rangle$ (cm/s)	[C ₂ H ₄]	Film Thickness, AFM (nm)	Film Thickness, Model* (nm)	R _s (Ω/sq)	T @550 nm (%)
40	0-20-20	0.09	0.5	237	242	-	-
140	120-10-10	0.61	0.07	10	10	-	-
	100-20-20		0.14	14	19	-	-
	80-30-30		0.21	17	29	-	-
	0-70-70		0.5	82	69	-	-
340	300-20-20	1.49	0.06	12	3	9800 ± 900	77.27
	190-75-75		0.22	11	13	-	-
	140-100-100		0.29	14	17	3100 ± 100	55.74
	0-170-170		0.5	13	29	5600 ± 800	52.34
540	500-20-20	2.37	0.04	5	1	7800 ± 1500	85.66
	420-60-60		0.11	8	4	6000 ± 200	80.39
	300-120-120		0.22	18	8	4200 ± 140	58.65
	0-270-270		0.5	15	18	5600 ± 400	63.11

Figure S1. Optimized gas flow and temperature schedule for carbon film synthesis, with key stages in the overall growth process identified. a) In the first stage ('flushing') ambient air is removed from the system (tube, lines and reactor). b) In the 'annealing' stage, the copper foil is annealed and then, a carbon film is synthesized in the 'growth' stage. c) The 'cooling down' stage is necessary to eliminate the reactive gases in the system before removing the grown carbon film.

Figure S2. Different colors of reacted gas can be observed during the synthesis of the carbon films, downstream the copper position. High flow rates with low ethylene concentration showed no visible gas (500-20-20), and a gray gas appeared for highly concentrated ethylene at low flow rates (0-20-20), at which condition carbon is

deposited in quartz, as shown in the comparative Raman spectra of copper and quartz slide.

Figure S3. Process followed to measure the thickness of the carbon films. The carbon film/copper foil was dipped in copper etchant. Once the copper foil was completely etched, we cleaned the carbon film with deionized water several times and then we “fished out” the remaining carbon film with a SiO₂ wafer. Finally, we measured the thickness of the film by AFM from a stepped surface.

Figure S4. Analysis of the “top carbon” and the “bottom carbon” by Raman spectroscopy. For the “top carbon”, we dipped the carbon film/copper and then we etched the copper. The remaining carbon film was “fished out” with a SiO₂ wafer and the “top carbon” was upward. For the “bottom carbon” analysis, we dipped the carbon film/copper upside down, and the bottom carbon was upward.

Figure S5. a) SEM carbon film (*ca.* 19 nm thick) on top of a copper foil synthesized by CVD and b) carbon films with different thicknesses transferred to PMMA.

Figure S6. TEM of carbon films showing fullerene-like fragments and amorphous regions. a) Low magnification image of a carbon film about 5 nm thick, and b) a detail of curved fullerene-like fragments. The same fullerene-like fragments were detected in samples of different thickness c) an 8-nm-thick carbon film synthesized by using 420-60-60 sccm of Ar-H₂-C₂H₄, and d) 15-nm-thick carbon film synthesized by using 0-270-270 sccm of Ar-H₂-C₂H₄.

Figure S7. Transmittance as a function of wavelength. Carbon films synthesized by using 340 sccm (a) and 540 sccm (b) of total flow. Film thickness and synthesis details (Ar:H₂:C₂H₄ flow in sccm) are indicated.

7. References

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